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**A Study on the Role of Technology Transformation in NBFCs
(With Reference to Muthoot Mini Financiers, Eriyodu)**

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ABSTRACT

Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs) play a crucial role in providing financial services, especially to underserved and rural populations. In recent years, technological advancements have significantly transformed the operations of NBFCs, particularly in the areas of loan processing, customer service, and operational efficiency. This study aims to analyze the role of technology transformation in NBFCs with special reference to Muthoot Mini Financiers Limited, Eriyodu branch.

The study focuses on comparing traditional and digital lending systems, identifying key technologies used, and understanding customer perception towards digital services. Primary data was collected from 100 respondents using a structured questionnaire. Statistical tools such as percentage analysis and Chi-square tests were used for analysis.

The study found that technology has improved loan processing speed, reduced paperwork, and enhanced customer satisfaction. However, challenges such as digital awareness gaps and technical issues still exist. The study suggests improving digital literacy and strengthening technological infrastructure in NBFCs.

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INTRODUCTION

Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs) are an important part of the Indian financial system. They provide loans and financial services to individuals and businesses, especially in areas where traditional banking services are limited.

Earlier, NBFCs followed manual processes such as physical documentation, branch visits, and slow loan approvals. These methods were time-consuming and less efficient. With the introduction of digital technologies, NBFCs have started adopting modern tools like:

- e-KYC verification
- Mobile applications
- Digital payment systems
- Automated loan processing

These technologies have improved speed, accuracy, and customer convenience. Today, customers can apply for loans online and receive approvals quickly.

This study focuses on how technology is transforming NBFC operations and improving customer experience.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“The NBFC sector faces critical challenges in operational efficiency, risk assessment, customer experience, and scalability due to its historically manual and paper-based processes. With increasing competition from digitally advanced FinTechs and rising customer expectations for speed and transparency, NBFCs must adopt modern technologies. This study examines how technology can transform NBFC operations and evaluates the impact of technological adoption across key functional areas.” This problem statement forms the foundation of the research.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To compare traditional and digital lending systems in NBFCs
2. To identify key technologies improving efficiency and service quality
3. To study customer perception towards digital NBFC services
4. To provide suggestions for improving digital adoption in NBFCs

NEED OF THE STUDY

NBFCs are rapidly adopting digital technologies to compete with banks and FinTech companies. Understanding how these technologies impact operations and customer satisfaction is important.

This study helps to:

- Identify benefits of digital transformation
- Understand customer expectations
- Improve service quality in NBFCs

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study is limited to:

- Muthoot Mini Financiers Limited, Eriyodu
- 100 respondents
- Focus on lending process and customer perception It

covers both traditional and digital NBFC services.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design: Descriptive research

Sources of Data:

- Primary Data: Questionnaire
- Secondary Data: Books, journals, websites

Sample Size: 100 respondents

Sampling Technique: Simple random sampling

Tools Used:

- Percentage analysis
- Chi-square test

- Tables and charts

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Previous studies show that technology has a major impact on financial services:

- Digital systems improve loan processing speed
- e-KYC reduces documentation
- Mobile apps increase customer convenience
- Data analytics improves decision-making

However, studies also highlight challenges such as:

- Lack of digital awareness
- Technical issues
- Resistance to change

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The study shows the following key findings:

- Majority of respondents are young (18–35 age group)
- 75% have taken loans from NBFCs
- Digital methods are becoming popular

Speed of Processing

Most respondents believe digital systems are faster.

Loan Approval Time

70% receive approval within one day.

Paperwork Reduction

75% agree that digital systems reduce paperwork.

Ease of Use

70% find digital applications easy.

Customer Satisfaction

Majority are satisfied with digital services.

Trust in Digital Platforms

Around 70% trust digital NBFC services.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H0: Technology has no impact

H1: Technology improves efficiency Based on

analysis:

- Digital systems are faster
- Customer satisfaction is higher
- Paperwork is reduced

Result:

H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected

This proves that technology significantly improves NBFC operations.

COMPLIANCE BURDEN

Compliance burden refers to the time, effort, and documentation required to complete NBFC loan processes. Traditional systems involve higher paperwork and manual procedures, whereas digital technologies reduce this burden through automation and simplified verification.

MAJOR DIFFICULTIES IN NBFC DIGITAL SERVICES

Customers face difficulties such as lack of digital awareness, technical issues, and concerns about data security. These challenges can affect the smooth adoption of digital NBFC services.

IMPROVEMENTS EXPECTED IN DIGITAL NBFC SERVICES

Customers expect faster processing, simplified procedures, improved system usability, and stronger data

security. Continuous technological enhancement is essential to improve customer experience.

IMPROVEMENT DO YOU EXPECT FROM DIGITAL NBFC SERVICES

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Faster Loan Approval	33	33.0	33.0
Easy Documentation	23	23.0	23.0
Better Customer Service	24	24.0	24.0
Online Access Anytime	20	20.0	20.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0

INTERPRETATION

The table shows that **faster loan approval (33%)** is the most important benefit of technology in NBFC services. This is followed by **better customer service (24%)** and **easy documentation (23%)**, while **20%** of respondents value online access.

Overall, the findings indicate that **speed and efficiency are the key advantages of digital transformation in NBFCs.**

FINDINGS

1. Digital lending is faster than traditional methods
2. Customers prefer mobile apps and online services
3. Technology reduces processing time and errors
4. Customer satisfaction is higher in digital systems
5. Some customers still face difficulty using digital platforms
6. Awareness level is mode

CHI-SQUARE

The Pearson Chi-Square value is 31.867 with 3 degrees of freedom, and the significance value (p-value) is 0.000, which is less than 0.05.

Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that there is a significant relationship between mode of loan application and processing speed among NBFC customers.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Provide training for customers on digital usage
2. Improve mobile applications and user interface
3. Reduce technical errors and server issues
4. Increase awareness programs in rural areas
5. Strengthen customer support services

CONCLUSION

Technology transformation has brought significant changes in the NBFC sector. Digital systems have improved efficiency, reduced processing time, and enhanced customer satisfaction.

However, some challenges still exist, such as lack of awareness and technical issues. To fully benefit from digital transformation, NBFCs must focus on customer education and system improvement.

Overall, technology plays a key role in modernizing NBFC operations and improving financial services in India.

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